

INFLUENCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY ON EFFECTIVE LEARNING OF BUSINESS EDUCATION AMONG PRE-SERVICE BUSINESS EDUCATORS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16710798>

Published: August 2025

Abstract

Information and Communication technology plays an integral role in learning in the learning of Business education. Therefore, this study examined the influence of Information and Communication Technology on effective learning of Business Education among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine the relevance of ICTs in the learning of ICTs as perceived by pre-service Business educators, the constraints militating against effective utilization of ICTs in the learning of Business Education as perceived by pre-service Business educators and how the effective utilization of ICTs for effective learning of Business education can be promoted. The study adopted the descriptive survey method, and questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. The sample of the study was selected using random sampling technique. Hence, a total of Two Hundred and Twelve (212) pre-service Business educators responded to the questionnaire, which was a researcher-designed questionnaire tagged Influence of Information and Communication Technology on Effective Learning of Business Education Questionnaire (IICTELBEQ)". The instrument was validated by experts and it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.75. The analysis of the data collected was done using both descriptive and inferential statistics of frequency count and percentage. The findings indicated that Information and Communication Technology is highly relevant to learning of Business Education courses among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria. Also, the identified constraints affecting the effective utilization of ICTs for learning of Business education in Lagos State include ICT equipment include poor implementation of ICT related courses, poor electricity supply, high cost of ICT facilities in Business Education laboratory., inadequate funding of Business education by the stakeholders, lack of experience of the lecturers teaching ICT, and a host of others, while the strategies for promoting the utilization of ICTs in the effective learning of Business Education in Lagos State, include employment of adequate qualified ICT compliance business educator lecturers by the stakeholders, adequate funding of ICT facilities by the stakeholders. The study recommended among others that, pre-service Business Educators should be trained and re-trained on how to harness the diverse relevance of Information and Communication Technology to improve their learning of Business Education in Universities in Lagos State, and adequate funding should be provided by stakeholders in the University system in Lagos State to help lecturers and students make the best use of ICT resources.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Relevance, Business Education, Pre-Service Business Educators, Constraints

Introduction

Education is globally acknowledged as one of the main drivers of the vehicle of the development process in the society. Thus, education policy makers, in recognition of the diverse potentials, have placed a great premium on the harnessing of the tool of education for individual and national development. The rationale for the foregoing is clearly articulated in the National Policy on Education which noted that no nation can rise above the quality of its educational system. Based on this self evident truth, the National Policy on Education broadly classifies the system for the deployment of formal education in Nigeria into three main categories, which includes the Basic school, senior secondary school and the level of tertiary education (Ajisafe, 2014).

Tertiary education in Nigeria is commonly referred to as the apex level of education. In relation to Nigeria, the goals of tertiary education, as spelt out in Section 5 sub-section 81 of the National Policy on Education (2013) are to: contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower training; provide accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities in formal and informal education in response to the needs and interests of all Nigerians; provide high quality career counselling and lifelong learning programmes that prepare students with the knowledge and skills for self-reliance and the world of work; reduce shortages through the production of skilled manpower relevant to the needs of the labour market; promote and encourage scholarship, entrepreneurship and community service; forge and cement national unity; and to promote national and international understanding and interaction.

To this end, therefore, Business Education is one of the courses offered by undergraduates and postgraduates in Nigerian universities. Essentially, Business Education is a branch of Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) or Technological and Vocational Education (TVE) that focuses on the production of the required manpower for the socio-economic development of the nation through the preparation and training of individuals for gainful employment and functional living through the means of skills acquisition and acquisition of the much-needed business knowledge (Oladunjoye, 2016).. In other words, Business Education is a course in the university curriculum that provides the socio-economic competence that is required for self-reliance in the society (Anaele, Shobowale, & Adhlakun, 2015; Ekoh, 2016; Azih & Nwagbara, 2018). Essentially, the broad goals of business education in the Nigerian university system is geared towards preparing students for the labour market, helping students to understand the dynamics of the Nigerian business and socio-economic systems, making students to be good consumers and producers of various goods and services, preparing students to harness their knowledge, attitude, skills, interests and competencies to start a business and also excel in the business sector, and helping students to understand the various career

opportunities in the free enterprise system as well as the local economy in Nigerian and the global economy (Adelakun, 2022; Oroka, Atarere, & Okifo, 2020).

In the contemporary university system, various forms of Information and Communication Technologies are increasingly being leveraged by Business Education lecturers and students to facilitate the effective learning of Business Education. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) comprises of electronic devices which are utilized to meet the information, communication and technology needs of users (Amahi & Odigili, 2021; Oghenetega, Okeke & Umeji, 2019). Abidoye and Omotunde (2020) defined ICTs as communication devices or applications such as mobile phones, radio, television, computers and its associated networks such as the internet and satellite systems. Likewise, Eseroghene and Barisi (2020) defined ICTs as technology systems used to automate, create, process, display, store, transmit and disseminate information. Etiubon and Akpan (2020) referred to Information and Communication Technology as a collection of software, hardware and services that are utilized by an individual, a group of persons and organizations to process information to achieve a pre-determined goal.

Examples of such ICT tools includes computers sets, computer and application software (that is spreadsheet, word processing, excel, PowerPoint), disc and storage media (that is memory cards, flash drives, scanner, CD-ROMs, audio and video cassettes, films, picture, e-books, e-magazines), telecommunication gadget and services such as web-based tools, mobile technologies, network software and hardware and other related online based technologies, such as blogs, social media, video conferencing, emails and a host of other extant and emerging technologies that are used for processing, storage, presentation, communication and exchange of data and information, such as Massively Open Online Courses (MOOCs), games and gamification, artificial intelligence, wearable technology, learning analytics, tablet computing, Google Classroom and Block Chain technology (Adelakun, Omolola & Adebola, 2022; Ajokpaniovo & Awoyemi, 2020; Nwankwoala, 2020, Umar, 2021; Zango, 2020).

Regardless of the diverse forms of ICTs, extant literature is replete with the various influences of ICTs on the teaching and learning of Business Education in the Nigerian tertiary education system. For instance, Anthony and Clever (2023) examined the influence of Information and Communication Technology on Business Education students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. The findings indicated that Business Education students are utilizing the available forms of ICT tools and that the availability of Information and Communication Technology had a significant influence of academic performance of

Business Education students in Delta State. Adejola and Okoye (2018) examined the ICT learning experiences of Business Education and their programme satisfaction in Universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings indicated that the extent of satisfaction of the Business Education students with ICT learning experiences was low and the relationship between the available ICT tools and the acquiring of learning experiences among the respondents was negative.

In another related study, Aleanor, Tambari, and Iyalla (2018) found out that Information and Communication Technology had a moderate and positive relationship between the academic performance of university students in Business education in selected universities in rivers State, Nigeria, and therefore recommended that Information and Communication technologies should be effectively integrated into the teaching and learning of Business Education in Nigerian universities. Agozie (2019) examined the influence of Information and Communication Technology on the academic performance of Business Education students in Rivers State, Nigeria and found out that ICTs had a significant influence on the academic performance of Business Education students because ICTs helps students to carry out individualized study, as well as in the searching for information and acquiring more information to update their knowledge.

While it is crystal clear that ICTs have great influences on the learning of Business Education among university students in Nigeria, it goes without saying that many challenges are militating against the effective integration, adoption and utilization of ICTs for learning of Business Education. In this regard, Ezeabii and Agomuo (2017) examined the various challenges hampering the effective teaching of business education in selected public universities in the South Eastern part of Nigeria and concluded that Business Education lecturers lack the required ICT skills to effectively use ICTs in their pedagogic practices, there is a lack of competent computer engineers to maintain the acquired ICT facilities, the foreign software are too expensive to be used by Business Education lecturers and students, and low level of funding as well as inadequate ICT in-service training for lecturers to keep the abreast of the latest developments in the application of ICTs into the teaching of Business Education were the main challenges affecting the integration of ICTs into the teaching of Business Education.

In another study, Ezeabii, Ekoh, and Okwor (2020) found that the challenges militating against the effective usage of the utilization of new technologies in the achievement of the goals of Business Education in public universities located in South-East, Nigeria are lack of funds to procure the much-needed ICT facilities, the negative role of politics in the implementation of technology adoption and integration in the public

universities, low level of governmental support for innovation in the teaching of Business Education in public universities, and lack of adequate and effective legal frameworks to support and drive the utilization of ICTs in the selected public universities. Given the foregoing, it appears that there is a dearth of related studies on the influence of Information and Communications Technology on the effective teaching and learning of Business Education in Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. Therefore, in order to fill the gap in extant literature, the problem of the present study was to investigate the influence of Information and Communication Technology on effective learning of Business education among pre-service Business educators in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the relevance of Information and Communication Technology in the learning of Business Education as perceived by pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria?
2. What are the constraints affecting the effective utilization of Information and Communication Technology in the in the learning of Business Education as perceived by pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria?
3. How can Information and Communication Technology be used to promote effective learning of Business education among pre-service Business educators in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Methodology

The survey research design was employed for the conduct of the study. The population for this study was all pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State. Two hundred and twelve (212) pre-service Business Educators, which includes 127 business education students from University of Lagos and 85 Business Education students from Lagos State University were selected from the population using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-designed questionnaire titled “Influence of Information and Communication Technology on Effective Learning of Business Education Questionnaire (IICTELBEQ)”. Section A of the questionnaire sought demographic information of respondents, such as gender and age, Section B with 7 items focused on relevance of ICTs in the learning of Business Education, Section C with 8 items focused on the constraints affecting the effective utilization of ICTs for learning of Business Education, while Section D with 8 items focused on how can ICTs be used to promote effective learning of Business Education among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State. Items in Sections B, C, and D were patterned in Likert scale format of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3

points, Disagree (D) = 2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point. The content validity of the questionnaire was established by expert opinion, while a re-test reliability correlation coefficient of 0.75 was obtained for the questionnaire, which was deemed reliable for the study. The data obtained was analyzed using frequency counts and percentages.

Results

Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Respondents Based on Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	109	51.4
Female	103	48.6
Total	212	100.0

Table 1 showed the demographic data of the respondents on the basis of gender. Thus, 109 (51.5%) of the respondents were males, while 103 (48.6%) of the respondents were females. This indicates that male pre-service Business Educators teachers participated in the study than their female counterparts.

Table 2.

Percentage Distribution of Respondents Based on Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 15 years	27	12.7
15-20 years	137	64.6
20 years and above	48	22.6
Total	212	100.0

Table 2 showed the demographic data of the respondents on the basis of age. Thus, 27(12.7%) of the respondents were less than 15 years of age in the institutions, 137 64.6% respondents were within the age bracket of 15-20 years, while 48 (22.6%) of the respondents were above 20 years. This table

shows that respondents that are between 15-20 years of age attended more to the questionnaires in the sampled universities.

Research Question One: What is the relevance of Information and Communication Technology in the learning of Business Education as perceived by pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Table 4.3 Percentage Distribution of the Relevance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the Learning of Business Education as Perceived By Pre-Service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria.

S/N	ITEMS	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	MEAN \bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	ICT helps to facilitates teaching between lecturers and students	73 (34.4)	87 (41.0)	38 (17.9)	14 (6.6)	3.0330	.88903	Accept
2	ICT facilitates interaction between lecturers and students	53 (26.0)	95 (44.8)	53 (25.0)	9 (4.2)	2.9292	.83166	Accept
3	ICT enhances effective storage of basic information	63 (29.7)	83 (39.2)	57 (26.9)	9 (4.2)	2.9434	.85797	Accept
4	ICT facilitates Business Education students to acquire necessary concepts without barriers	55 (25.9)	96 (45.3)	50 (23.6)	11 (5.2)	2.9198	.83648	Accept
5	ICT enhances physical involvement of the learners	61 (28.8)	93 (43.9)	50 (23.6)	8 (3.8)	2.9764	.82290	Accept
6	ICT helps to maximize students' attentiveness to instruction	47 (22.2)	95 (44.8)	58 (27.4)	12 (5.7)	2.8396	.84469	Accept
7	ICT resource utilization makes teaching to be stimulating	49 (23.1)	75 (35.4)	58 (27.4)	30 (14.2)	2.6745	.98458	Accept

Average means score = 2.50 $\bar{x} < \text{Mean score} = \text{Reject}$ $\bar{x} > \text{Mean score} = \text{Accept}$

Response to the question in table 4.3 above shows that majority of the respondents, that is, 75.4% agreed that ICT helps to facilitates teaching between lecturers and students. Similarly, 70.8% respondents believe that ICT facilitates interaction between lecturers and students. On the other hand, also 68.9% of the respondents believe that ICT enhances effective storage of basic information. 71.2% of the respondents believe that ICT facilitates Business Education students to acquire necessary concepts without barriers. 72.7% agreed that through ICT enhances physical involvement of the learners. 67.0% of the respondents are of the opinion that ICT helps to maximize students' attentiveness to instruction. Finally, 58.5% of the respondents believe that ICT resource utilization makes teaching to be stimulating.

Research Question Two: What are the constraints affecting the effective utilization of Information and Communication Technology in the in the learning of Business Education as perceived by pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Table 4.4 Percentage Distribution of the constraints affecting the effective utilization of Information and Communication Technology in the in the learning of Business Education as perceived by pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria

<i>SN</i>	<i>ITEMS</i>	<i>SA</i> (%)	<i>A</i> (%)	<i>D</i> (%)	<i>SD</i> (%)	<i>MEAN</i> \bar{X}	<i>SD</i>	<i>Remark</i>
8	Inadequate ICT equipment	43 (20.3)	76 (35.8)	56 (26.4)	37 (17.5)	2.5896	1.00070	<i>Accept</i>
9	Poor implementation of ICT related courses	54 (25.5)	72 (34.0)	52 (24.5)	34 (16.0)	2.6887	1.02447	<i>Accept</i>
10	Poor electricity supply	40 (18.9)	75 (35.4)	75 (35.4)	22 (10.4)	2.6274	.90695	<i>Accept</i>
11	High cost of ICT facilities in Business Education laboratory	61 (28.8)	76 (35.8)	48 (22.6)	27 (12.7)	2.8066	.99542	<i>Accept</i>
12	Inadequate funding from the stakeholders	43 (20.3)	70 (33.0)	65 (30.7)	34 (16.0)	2.5755	.98758	<i>Accept</i>
13	Inadequate experience of the lecturers teaching ICT	44 (20.8)	75 (34.4)	58 (27.4)	35 (16.5)	2.6038	.99458	<i>Accept</i>
14	Inadequate ICT software's	65 (30.7)	81 (38.2)	49 (23.1)	17 (8.0)	2.9151	.92483	<i>Accept</i>
15	Lack of internet facilities	38 (17.9)	80 (37.7)	68 (32.1)	26 (12.3)	2.6132	.91921	<i>Accept</i>

Average means score = 2.50 $\bar{x} < \text{Mean score} = \text{Reject}$ $\bar{x} > \text{Mean score} = \text{Accept}$

Response to the Research Question in Table 4.3 above shows that majority of the respondents i.e. 56.1% agreed that ICT equipment are not adequate in Business Laboratory. Similarly, 59.5% respondents believe that there is poor implementation of ICT related courses. So also, 54.4 of the respondents are of the opinion that one of the major constraints facing business education is poor electricity supply. On the other hand, 64.6% of the respondents believe that there is high cost of ICT facilities in Business Education laboratory. So also, 53.3% of the respondents believe that Business education is not adequately funded by the stakeholders. 55.2% agreed that the lecturers teaching ICT and Business related courses are not experienced technologically. 68.9% also believe the statement that there is lack of adequate ICT software's for teaching and learning of business related courses. Finally, 55.6% of the respondents is of the opinion that business education laboratory lacks of internet facilities for effective integration of ICT to classroom.

Research Question Two: How can Information and Communication Technology be used to promote effective learning of Business education among pre-service Business educators in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Table 4.5 Percentage Distribution of how Information and Communication Technology can be used to promote effective learning of Business education among pre-service Business educators in Lagos State, Nigeria

<i>SN</i>	<i>ITEMS</i>	<i>SA</i> (%)	<i>A</i> (%)	<i>D</i> (%)	<i>SD</i> (%)	<i>MEAN</i> \bar{X}	<i>SD</i>	<i>Remark</i>
16	Employment of adequate qualified ICT compliance business educator lecturers by the stakeholders	54 (25.5)	94 (44.3)	52 (24.5)	12 (5.7)	2.8962	.84796	<i>Accept</i>
17	Adequate funding of ICT facilities by the stakeholders	66 (31.2)	79 (37.3)	51 (24.1)	16 (7.5)	2.9245	.93076	<i>Accept</i>
18	Provision of adequate ICT facilities by the stakeholders	53 (25.0)	101 (47.6)	45 (21.2)	13 (6.1)	2.9151	.83884	<i>Accept</i>
19	Proper implementation of ICT related courses by the stakeholders	57 (26.9)	90 (42.5)	49 (23.1)	16 (7.5)	2.8868	.89040	<i>Accept</i>
20	ICT helps students to demonstrate the understanding of what have been taught	68 (32.1)	73 (34.4)	52 (24.5)	19 (9.0)	2.8962	.95817	<i>Accept</i>
21	Students positive attitude towards ICT related courses	61 (28.8)	96 (45.3)	49 (23.1)	6 (2.8)	3.0000	.79691	<i>Accept</i>
22	Provision of standardize Business education laboratory	73 (34.4)	72 (34.0)	54 (25.5)	13 (6.1)	2.9670	.92046	<i>Accept</i>

Average means score = 2.50 $\bar{x} < Mean score = Reject \bar{x} > Mean score = Accept$

Response to the question in table 4.4 above shows that majority of the respondents i.e. 69.8% agreed that Employment of adequate qualified ICT compliance business educator lecturers by the stakeholders will bring about improvement in teaching and learning process of business education. Similarly, 68.5% respondents

believes that adequate funding of ICT facilities by the stakeholders will promote effective teaching and learning of business education as well as the standard of business education in general. On the other hand, 72.6% of the respondents believe that Provision of adequate ICT facilities in business laboratory by the stakeholders will bring about improvement in teaching and learning process. So also, 69.4% of the respondents believe that when there is proper implementation of ICT related courses by the stakeholders the standard of business education will be improved upon. 66.5% of the respondents agreed that ICT and its related gargets helps students to demonstrate the understanding of what they have been taught effectively without any barrier. 74.1% are also of the opinion that students show positive attitudes towards the use of ICT and internet related courses. Finally, 68.4% of the respondents are of the opinion that adequate provision of a modern business education laboratory will improve the standard of business education.

Summary of Findings

1. Information and Communication Technology is highly relevant to learning of Business Education courses among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria.
2. The constraints affecting the effective utilization of ICTs for learning of Business education in Lagos State include ICT equipment are not adequate in Business Laboratory, poor implementation of ICT related courses, poor electricity supply, high cost of ICT facilities in Business Education laboratory., Inadequate funding of Business education by the stakeholders, lack of experience of the lecturers teaching ICT, and a host of others.
3. The measures for promoting the effective use of ICTs in the effective learning of Business Education courses among pre-service teachers in Lagos State include Employment of adequate qualified ICT compliance business educator lecturers by the stakeholders, adequate funding of ICT facilities by the stakeholders, provision of adequate ICT facilities in business laboratory by the stakeholders, proper implementation of ICT related courses by the stakeholders, provision of ICT and its related gargets, promotion of students' positive attitudes towards the use of ICT and internet related courses, and adequate provision of a modern business education laboratory.

Discussion of Findings

Owing to the rapid and widespread development of Information and Communication Technology in the 21st century, the adoption and integration of ICT tools in the teaching and learning of Business education has become a necessity. Therefore, this study examined the influence of Information and Communication Technology on effective learning of Business education among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State,

Nigeria. Essentially the findings indicated that Information and Communication Technology is highly relevant to learning of Business Education courses among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria. Specifically, the respondents indicated that ICTs are relevant in the learning of Business Education because it helps to facilitates teaching between lecturers and students, facilitates interaction between lecturers and students, enhances effective storage of basic information, facilitates Business Education students to acquire necessary concepts without barriers, enhances physical involvement of the learners, helps to maximize students' attentiveness to instruction, and makes teaching to be stimulating. This finding could be attributed to the fact that many of the respondents are netizens who were born in the digital age and therefore grew up using various ICT tools to perform a broad spectrum of functions within and outside the University environment.

The second finding of the study indicated that the constraints affecting the effective utilization of ICTs for learning of Business education in Lagos State include ICT equipment are not adequate in Business Laboratory, poor implementation of ICT related courses, poor electricity supply, high cost of ICT facilities in Business Education laboratory., Inadequate funding of Business education by the stakeholders, lack of experience of the lecturers teaching ICT, and a host of others. This finding could be as a result of the personal, university based and Government based problems that pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State face in the utilization of various ICT tools to learn Business Education courses.

In order to remedy the constraints affecting the effective utilization of ICTs and to promote the utilization of ICTs in the effective learning of Business Education in Lagos State, the findings in Table 4.3. indicated that employment of adequate qualified ICT compliance business educator lecturers by the stakeholders, adequate funding of ICT facilities by the stakeholders, provision of adequate ICT facilities in business laboratory by the stakeholders, proper implementation of ICT related courses by the stakeholders, provision of ICT and its related gargets, promotion of students' positive attitudes towards the use of ICT and internet related courses, and adequate provision of a modern business education laboratory will greatly promote the use of ICTs for learning among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State.

Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of Information and Communication Technology on effective learning of Business education among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it could be concluded that Information and Communication Technology is highly relevant to learning of Business Education courses among pre-service Business Educators in Lagos State, Nigeria, the constraints affecting the effective utilization of ICTs for learning of Business education in Lagos State include ICT

equipment include poor implementation of ICT related courses, poor electricity supply, high cost of ICT facilities in Business Education laboratory., inadequate funding of Business education by the stakeholders, lack of experience of the lecturers teaching ICT, and a host of others, while the strategies for promoting the utilization of ICTs in the effective learning of Business Education in Lagos State, include employment of adequate qualified ICT compliance business educator lecturers by the stakeholders, adequate funding of ICT facilities by the stakeholders and provision of adequate ICT facilities in business laboratory by the stakeholders among others.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are advanced:

1. Pre-service Business Educators should be trained and re-trained on how to harness the diverse relevance of Information and Communication Technology to improve their learning of Business Education in Universities in Lagos State.
2. Lecturers should be mandated and encouraged to enroll in in-service ICT capacity building seminars and workshops so as to improve the integration of ICTs into the teaching and learning of Business education.
3. In order to overcome the identified constraints of the utilization of ICTs in Business education, adequate funding should be provided by stakeholders in the University system in Lagos State to help lecturers and students make the best use of ICT resources.
4. Further research study should be carried out on students of other academic courses in Nigeria federal universities in order to test the relevance of information and communication technology as a tool for enhancing students learning and academic performance.
5. Similar studies should also be carried out in other tertiary institutions such as the Polytechnics and Colleges of Education.

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